

RESEARCH ON MT300/603A COMPOSITE MATERIAL AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY

Zhang Jianbao, Wang Junfeng, Ling Hui, Sun Hongjie, Jiang Wenge

Aerospace Research Institute of Materials & Processing Technology, Beijing 100076 ,
www.arimt.com

Keywords: Composite, MT300/603A, AFP, Prepreg, Hook face conical shell

ABSTRACT

Based on the application situation of the fiber placement home and abroad, the processing property and advantages were analyzed. The prepreg tow for fiber placement was selected and affirmed, according to the processing property test. After that, the processing experiments of unidirectional laminate and laminate were made, and the composite hook surface conical shell test cell was developed and performance evaluated. The research results show that the material MT300/603A is suitable for fiber placement, and the hook surface conical shell have a good quality.

1 INTRODUCTION

Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) is a key technology for the manufacturing of composites parts. It has been used for many years in the aeronautic industry for panels, barrels, vessels, beams and primary structure production^[1]. Now , AFP is being widely used in the aerospace industry as a cost-effective manufacturing technique to build primary composite structures. Its advantage is firstly the ability to place tows at the right place with correct angles, compared with fabric or large tape lay-up (by hand or other equipment), especially for primary structures, large parts and complex surface structures^[2, 3].

In fibre placement processing, the composite material is laid down on a tool or prior lamina by a machine tool or robot fitted with a multiple small tows placement head. Prepreg Tows are fed from the storage installed in the head, or a separate storage module on machine tool.

The typical width is 6.35 mm (1/4 inch) for automated fibre placement machines, and the most widely used material nowadays is thermoset prepreg tow, compared with thermoplastic tow and dry fibre material. First of all, the main advantage of thermoset prepreg tow is that it is easy to stick to mould surface or prior lamina on the surface in the fibre placement processing. Second, the heating temperature of thermoset prepreg tow is smaller than other tows, and is easy to supported and controlled accurately by machine. Therefore, the material damage from excess heating is hold back in the placement processing. Third, it is more suitable for fiber steering placement, according to the tow with more deform property than hermo plastics one.

No matter how good thermoset tow is, the disadvantages are present in the manufacturing processing. The tows have a tackiness, which causes the fibre placement machine with complex system used to corresponding solution. The plastic backing tows are applied to prevent the prepreg tows from getting stuck between each other. Whereas, the plastic backing tows then have to be removed during the fibre placement processing after feeding out from the cool storage. The creels, tubes and other components in the head have to be cooled to prevent the prepreg tows from getting stuck.

Epoxy resins are the main thermosetting polymers applied in aerospace. However, not all of the epoxy prepreg is suitable for automated fiber placement, because of the tackiness changing with the tow temperature turning high or low. In this paper, MT300/603A prepreg tows were selected and affirmed by automated fiber placement processing, according to unidirectional laminate experiment, laminate experiment and hook face conical shell experiment. And the flaw area, fiber volume content and void content of hook surface conical shell were tested for the MT300/603A manufacturing quality evaluation.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials

The unidirectional prepreg MT300/603A was from Aerospace research institute of Materials & processing technology, and fabricated by way of a hot-melting process. The prepreg areal weight was set to 165 g/m² and the nominal resin content was (34±2) wt%. Prepreg was cut into tows with 6.35mm bandwidth (see Fig.1).

Fig. 1 prepreg tows

2.2 Unidirectional laminate fabrication and testing

The above prepreg tow was laid up to a required orientation and thickness, using a SKPF3000 AFP machine. The AFP processing was showed in Fig. 2. And the results between AFP and hand lay-up were compared and analyzed. The specimen configurations and test procedures were in accordance with GB/T 3354-1999, GB/T 3856-2005, GB/T 3356-1999 and Q/Dq 281-96. The dimension of specimen is 20mm×10mm×2mm for Q/Dq281-96. The mechanical properties of composite unidirectional laminates were tested in uniaxial tension, uniaxial compression, flexural and interlaminar shear at room temperature. Tests were conducted on MTS-SANS CMT5000 conducts the tests with a 100 kN capacity load cell. The reported mechanical properties were the average of at least five samples.

Fig. 2 composite unidirectional laminates and fiber placement processing

2.3 Laminate fabrication and testing

The laminate (see Fig. 3) was laid up by AFP with the above cutting tows. The test laminate had 16 MT300/603A plies (each 0.15mm thick) arranged in a $[\pm 45]_4s$ stacking sequence. The specimen configurations and test procedures were in accordance with GB/T3355-2005 and Q/Dq 281-96. The dimension of interlaminar shear specimen is 20mm×10mm×2mm for Q/Dq 281-96. Tests were conducted on MTS-SANS CMT5000 conducts the tests with a 100 kN capacity load cell. The reported mechanical properties were the average of at least five samples.

Figure 3: composite laminate and fiber placement processing

2.4 Hook face conical shell fabrication and testing

The hook face conical shell was laid up by AFP with the MT300/603A prepreg tows. The shell laminate had 16 MT300/603A plies (each 0.15mm thick) arranged in a $[\pm 45/0/\pm 30/90/\pm 45]_s$ stacking sequence (see Figure 4). After curing, the quality of the hook surface conical shell was tested and observed with ultrasonic flaw detection, according to DqES219-88. The fiber volume content and void content were tested according to GB/T 3366-1996 and GB 3365-82.

Figure 4: AFP Processing of hook surface conical shell

The cross sections at hook face conical shell laminates were observed using a Nikon Eclipse L150 microscope. Digital micrographs of prominent features were acquired and treated, utilizing a Clemex Captiva camera attachment connected to a desktop computer.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 unidirectional laminate properties

Table 1 provides a summary of tensile properties of unidirectional laminate at room temperatures, which were made by AFP and hand-layup respectively. The two kinds of composite laminates have almost the same fiber volume, 57.1% and 56.8% respectively, with identical curing conditions. The tensile strength and tensile modulus of AFP are 1410MPa and 120GPa, which decreases by 4.0% and 2.4% than those of hand-layup ones. And the coefficient of variation is sizable between the two kinds of laminates, which are both smaller than 10%. According to the coefficient of variation 10% for composite mechanical properties, the tensile properties of these unidirectional laminates fabricated by AFP and hand-layup are basically in the same level.

Test	AFP tensile strength/MPa	AFP tensile modulus/GPa	Hand-layup tensile strength/MPa	Hand-layup tensile modulus/GPa
\bar{X}	1410	120	1469	123
Cv	4.8%	2.6%	4.8%	2.3%

Table1: Mechanical properties of composite unidirectional laminate

3.2 laminate properties

The mechanical properties of MT300 reinforced composite laminate with the $[\pm 45]_4s$ stacking sequence are shown in table 2. The interlaminar shear strength of composite laminate is 72.4Mpa, and the coefficient of variation is 5.8%. The longitudinal transverse shear strength and modulus are 93.0MPa and 4.24GPa, with the coefficients of variation bellow 5%.

Test	\bar{X}	Cv
Inter laminar shear strength/MPa	72.4	5.8%
Longitudinal transverse shear strength/MPa	93.0	4.4%
Longitudinal transverse shear modulus/GPa	4.24	1.4%

Tab.2 Mechanical properties of composite laminate

3.3 hook face conical shell properties

The hook face conical shell before curing was shown in Fig. 5a. The layup edge of composite shell was cut down. Prepreg tows were compacted on the mould tool or the prior lamina, and the gap and overlap were between tows is accurately controlled by AFP machine. The tow bending and wrinkle were not observed by eyes. The hook face conical shell after curing was seen in Fig. 5b. The quality of the shell was tested and observed with ultrasonic flaw detection, and the flaw area is 0.05% compared structure shell total area, which is far lower than 1%.

Figure 5: Hook face conical shell: a) before curing; b) after curing

Table 3 provides the fiber volume content and void content of the hook face conical shell. The fiber volume content and void content are 57.9% and 0, respectively.

Test	fiber volume content/%	Void content/%
1	57.9%	0%
2	57.8%	0%
3	58.1%	0%
\bar{X}	57.9%	0%

Table 3: Fiber volume content and void content of hook face conical shell

The processing quality of the hook face conical shell structure was investigated with ultrasonic flaw detection, fiber volume content and voids content. According to the test result, the fabricated structure made by AFP with MT300/603A has a good quality, and will be applied in primary structure in the future.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the results show that the material MT300/603A prepreg tows are suitable for fiber placement processing with serialization tests, including unidirectional laminate experiment, laminate experiment and hook face conical shell test. According to the test results from ultrasonic flaw detection, fiber volume content and voids content, the fabricated structure made by AFP with MT300/603A has a good quality, and will be applied in primary structure in the future.

Further study should be performed in order to have more kinds of prepreg tows fit for AFP, and to manufacture bigger complex structures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study is financially supported by the Fundamental National Defence Research Project of China (No. 513120101).

The authors would like to thank Mr. Xiao Jun and Mr. Zhao Cong from Nanjing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics for their help and support in MT300/603A laminates processing with automated fiber placement machine in the early stage of this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] Michael I. N. G. Automated Tape Laying . *ASM Handbook, vol. 21: Composites, DB Miracle and S. Donaldson editors*, pp. 480-485.
- [2] Gurdal, Zafer, et al. Tow-Placement Technology and Fabrication Issues for Laminated Composite Structures, *46th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Austin, Texas, 2005*, April 18-21, pp. 18 p.
- [3] Grimshaw M N. Automated Tape Laying. *Materials Park, OH: ASM International, 2001*: 480-485.